

POSTLAR.UZ (FILE, PICTURE, VIDEO, MUSIC ... POSSIBILITY TO RECEIVE POST) WEB PAGE AND ITS VALIDITY

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Annotation: This article explains the importance of comments on a new web page. In addition, on this page, it is possible to receive video image files in text format.

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If you open the first page of any book, you can immediately see a brief introduction about it. It's abstract. In general, it is a short description of any work, whether it is a work of fiction, a dissertation or an article. And it depends on how clearly it is presented, whether the publisher or the reader is interested in this research.

The word "note" goes back to the Latin word *annotatio* - comment. It can also be called a resume ("abbreviated" - from the French). Actually and other sources have the essence of this genre.

When authors are tasked with writing comments on articles, they should remember that the main idea of the future publication should be expressed in a few sentences. And this should be done very briefly and as reliably as possible. The official recommended length of such a resume usually does not exceed 1000 characters.

This genre of scientific and informative method consists of two mandatory parts. In the first, the source is clearly described, the purpose set by the author, his main idea and scope of research are defined. Also, the work methodology and obtained results are described. The second part defines the intended audience of the

commented article. In this case, you need to clearly define how accurate the presentation language is.

In some cases, the comments of the articles may contain additional information. It is appropriate to talk about the content and structure of the resource, as well as familiarize yourself with the visual materials used in it. In conclusion, it will not be appropriate to show what new thoughts and ideas were expressed by the author in the research, to introduce him with his conclusions or recommendations.

You need to understand the type of key phrases you need to include in your text. Sentences help the reader to better understand what is discussed in the publication, whether to refer to the main content, etc.

So, here is a list of some phrases and turns that are often used when commenting on a scientific article. This is the type of thing that should be present in the result you want to get.

1. This article helps to address the problem.
2. The publication reviews the topic.
3. A scientific article is devoted to research.
4. Special attention was given by the author.
5. This problem has been little studied so far and therefore requires more detailed research.
6. The publication provides comprehensive and detailed analysis.

Of course, this is not a complete list of expressions and turns that can be used, you can always find more suitable ones. But these phrases are as appropriate as possible and allow readers to understand the main meaning of the whole text.

Depending on the character, this genre can be divided into two groups. The first involves annotating links to articles. Their purpose is to draw the reader's attention to the specific features of this work, to the level of information presented. What should be noted here? It is necessary:

- reveal the main idea of the title,
- briefly describe the content,

- providing necessary information about the author,
- if there are pictures, tell about it and describe them,
- define the target audience.

A more complex form of comment is a recommendation. It differs from a reference in that it may contain elements of criticism. With the help of such explanatory arguments, readers can be persuaded or persuaded to familiarize themselves with the proposed publication. In addition to the usual information about the author, comments or comments about the content of the work, an advisory note for a research paper evaluates the research. At the same time, it is compared with other similar works.

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